

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN CREATING PEDAGOGICAL SOFTWARE TOOLS

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Abstract. This article talks about the importance of application programs, i.e. information technologies, in the creation of software tools, the creation of personal computers using software tools.

Keywords: information technology, computer, Dream Weaver, Microsoft Frontpage, HTML.

ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ СОЗДАНИИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОГРАММНЫХ СРЕДСТВ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о значении прикладных программ, т.е. информационных технологий, в создании программных средств, создании персональных компьютеров с использованием программных средств.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии, компьютер, Dream Weaver, главная страница Microsoft, HTML.

It is not for nothing that they associate the progress of information technology with the invention of personal computers. The reason for this is that the need for software tools responsible for information technology has increased as a result of the advent of personal computers and is becoming a daily need. One of the important achievements in the application of personal computers to the educational process is the creation of a multimedia system (tools). The use of software tools responsible for information technologies is connected with the creation of personal computers, which created opportunities for the wide-scale application of multimedia, that is, sound, graphics, animation, and video tools to the educational system. These include virtual library and virtual teaching technologies.

Due to the new information technologies, opportunities for automation of management, administration, and provision of automated management of financial affairs have begun to appear. In addition, editors, software tools that translate from one language to another, which have great potential due to new information technologies, can be cited, the creation of which is also effective in the education system. These include HTML editors such as Macromedia Dream Weaver, Microsoft Front Page, and other software tools such as Microsoft Word, Adobe Photoshop, CorelDraw, Macromedia Flash. Of these, HTML is a hypertext markup language created for use in Internet technologies, and its documents (written in ASCII codes) consist of plain text files. They contain specially marked codes. Microsoft Front Page, Macromedia Dream Weaver and several similar special hardware tools are used to create and edit HTML documents.

In addition, HTML documents can be created using the following simple tools:

- Microsoft Windows NotePad (notepad), Windows Write editors;
- Microsoft Word editor, Word Perfect or optional editors that work in ASCII code and other text mode. As you can see, an optional (some kind of) plain text editor is needed to create an HTML document.

When working in Microsoft Windows NotePad or Write editor, to save the HTML document in text format, you should use the command "Sochranit kak" => "*.html".

HTML documents are distinguished from ordinary text files by a special character code (tag). These codes perform formatting of the document, determining the ready layout, expressing references to other documents and many other actions. HTML - codes are usually written in capital letters. This, in turn, makes them easier to distinguish from the main text and easier to edit.

Viewing the result of an HTML document written in special codes is done through a program known as a browser. Internet Explorer and NetsCape Navigator are the most commonly used browsers for HTML documents. The browser does not have the ability to edit the HTML document, it only displays it. You can edit an HTML document using the Microsoft Windows NotePad hardware tool without leaving the browser.

Creating HTML documents using simple hardware tools (Microsoft Windows NotePad, Microsoft Write, and similar simple text editors) by inserting special character codes requires a lot of time and a good knowledge of them. Another challenge is that it takes a lot of work to design an HTML document beautifully and place its objects optimally. To create an HTML document using the Microsoft Word editor, you do not need to manually write special character code. Even when we write special character code in Word, it is treated as plain text. Because Word is not designed to enter the code of an HTML document. To create an HTML document in the Microsoft Word editor, it is necessary to directly create its final view, that is, the view displayed by the browser, and save it to memory in the "*.html" format. A convenient aspect of creating an HTML document using Microsoft Word is that the resulting view can be created. The special character code is created by Microsoft Word itself.

One of the disadvantages of creating an HTML document using the Microsoft Word editor is that it takes up a lot of disk space. Creating or editing an HTML document using special software tools has great possibilities. Because special software tools provide an opportunity to work with HTML - the special character code of the document and the resulting appearance at the same time. Special software tools differ in their capabilities.

The size of the HTML document created with the help of special software is somewhat smaller. It is convenient to display it in the browser, and the internal hyperlinks organized in it work flawlessly even when moved to other directories.

When installing images in HTML documents, first of all, you should pay attention to their format. Images in different formats have different quality and size. For example, images in BMP (Bit Map Page) format, despite having high quality, take up a lot of disk space. JPEG (Joint Photographic Expert Group) format images have a quality level close to BMP and are almost twice as small. GIF (Graphic Interchange Format) format images have a very small size, only its image quality is much lower than BMP and JPG. In addition, the quality of these images also depends on which graphic editor is processed.

HTML uses animations to make a document look good. Animations come in different formats, and one of the most common and commonly used ones at the moment is GIF animation. Several special software tools are used to create GIF animations. For example, Ulead Cool 3D, Ulead Gif Animator, Macromedia Flash, etc. Each of these software tools has its own role in creating animations. Ulead Cool 3D, Ulead Gif animator software tools have great capabilities in animating texts, these software tools provide examples of all animations and their text input fields. After entering the text, the desired animation is selected.

Macromedia Flash is one of the best software tools when it comes to animating images. Using this software, you can create not only GIF, but also SWF and video (avi) animations. One of the important aspects is that animations can be saved in arbitrary formats. Macromedia Flash primarily saves animation in FLA format. Animation in this format only works in the Macromedia Flash environment. The advantage of this format is that the animation can be re-edited at will.

Because files saved in SWF and video format cannot be edited (changed). In the Macromedia Flash software, animations can be printed in HTML format, and a SWF format file is created as its basis. Animations in the SWF format are larger in size than others, have the ability to include sound, music, and therefore can also be controlled. HTML documents can use video files as animations, but the video files will be very large. This means that it takes more time to display the HTML document in the browser! - means. Macromedia Flash is one of the best tools for creating two-dimensional animations.

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